

101132933 – AD-RIDDLE

Real-World Implementation, Deployment and Validation of Early Detection Tools and Lifestyle Enhancement

WP9 – Program coordination, project management, and sustainability

D9.2 Data Management Plan (DMP)

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Description
V0.1	15/05/2024	First draft for internal review
V1.0	13/06/2024	Revised version following the KoM held on the 3-4 June.
V1.1	17/06/2024	Final contributions made by ULEIC team (WP6)
V1.2	24/06/2024	Internal review made by Wiese. M.van der Flier (VUMC)
V1.3	25/06/2024	Internal review made by Alina Solomon (UEF)
V1.3	28/06/2024	Internal review made by Ana Díaz and Dianne Gove (AE)
V2.0	26/07/2024	Final review and editing to produce a version for submission to IHI JU
V2.1	30/07/2024	Final version for submission to IHI JU

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the AD-RIDDLE Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

RS: Region Stockholm - Sweden (**Project Coordinator**)

KI: Karolinska Institutet - Sweden

FBHI: Stiftelsen Fingers Brain Health Institute - Sweden

UGOT: Goteborgs Universitet - Sweden

ULUND: Lunds Universitet - Sweden

UEF: Itäلتältä-suomen Yliopisto, University of Eastern Finland - Finland

STICHTING VUMC: Stichting VUMC - The Netherlands

UM: Universiteit Maastricht - The Netherlands

BBRC: Fundacion Barcelonaβeta Brain Research Center - Spain

SYNAPSE: Synapse Research Management Partners SL - Spain

AE: Alzheimer Europe - Luxembourg

ADI: Alzheimer's Disease International The International Federation of Alzheimer's Disease and Related Disorders Societies INC – United States

UNIPG: Università degli studi di Perugia - Italy

GV: Gates Ventures LLC – United States

DAC: Davos Alzheimer's collaborative - Switzerland

OY COMBINOSTICS: OY Combinostics oy - Finland

Fujirebio : Fujirebio Europe NV - Belgium

SARD : Sanofi-Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France

C2N: C2N Diagnostics LLC – United States

Neotiv GmbH: neotiv GmbH - Germany

CCL: Cambridge Cognition Limited - United Kingdom

ULEIC: University of Leicester - United Kingdom

IMPERIAL: Imperial College of Science Technology and Medicine - United Kingdom

NICE: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence - United Kingdom

Grant agreement

The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IHI for the undertaking of the AD-RIDDLE project (101132933).

Project

The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.

Consortium

The AD-RIDDLE Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.

Consortium agreement

Agreement concluded amongst AD-RIDDLE participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the current data management plans for the AD-RIDDLE project, covering aspects related to research data quality, sharing, and security, and the plans for making project data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reproducible). This Data Management Plan is also enriched by AD-RIDDLE collaborations with other EU-funded projects, especially EPND, and it follows the structure of data and knowledge management plans provided by European Commission guidelines.

The metadata catalogue and data flows used and generated by AD-RIDDLE will be initially held within the project to allow them to be reviewed by the partners for the sensitivity of their content. If it is deemed appropriate to share metadata more widely outside, WP6 along with relevant partners will review potential avenues for creating permanent links (such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs), ARK (data management system)) for those resources that are deemed acceptable by the partners to share outside of the project from an ethical or legal perspective.

It is important to note that the plans outlined in this document are not static and will develop over the project's life cycle, as the datasets and policies of related projects might evolve. This is an Initial Data Management Plan in that context, and future versions of this document will be established during the project's existence. The updated DMP will be set in deliverable D9.6 to be submitted by month 30.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Deliverable D9.2 of the Description of Action (DoA) is the first version of the Data Management Plan for the AD-RIDDLE project.

The plan set out in this document relates to the work to be performed as part of the Data Management of the project linked to WP6 which will actively track, record, and ‘orchestrate’ the necessary data management workflows. This is expected to encompass metadata, results, algorithms, data formats/transformations, sharing conditions/governance, and wider collaboration/sharing with the community. The approach will support requirements relevant to academic/research work in the project (e.g., cohort data, algorithm development, assay optimization), as well as data interactions involving healthcare settings that are implementing the project’s diagnostics solution.

The strategy outlined in this document will be periodically revised throughout the project as necessary, especially as the datasets and associated project policies change. The following sections have been organized in a manner that closely complies with the directions for such documents given by the European Commission for Horizon Europe.

Overview of AD-RIDDLE

The project aims to **develop a screening toolbox platform** that can be scaled across the EU for seamless patient flow and decision support for personalized prediction, early accurate diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease, and dementia preventive therapies.

The AD-RIDDLE platform is envisioned to revolutionize how AD is detected, diagnosed, prevented, and treated across healthcare settings (HCS). AD-RIDDLE centres around a toolbox platform concept, providing a series of validated tools at each key step to enable HCS and practitioners to deploy enhanced AD management across diverse patient populations.

The AD-RIDDLE toolbox platform will include community outreach tools, a combination of easily available, clinically validated biomarkers (both digital cognition and blood-based), and validated algorithms supporting clinical decisions, to identify people who can benefit from specific preventive therapies (pharmaceutical and/or non-pharmaceutical). The toolbox usability and efficacy will be tested in real-world settings.

An overview of the future AD-RIDDLE platform is displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overview of the AD-RIDDLE platform

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For all of its data management activities, AD-RIDDLE plans to leverage the European Platform for Neurodegenerative Diseases (EPND) platform. EPND (<https://epnd.org/>) is an IHI (former IMI) project that shares a number of key partners with AD-RIDDLE, and that aims to foster collaboration in neurodegeneration research by facilitating data and sample sharing. Figure 2 depicts a summarised view of EPND’s value proposition. Collaboration with EPND will also establish connections with other relevant data management platforms in the field, such as the Alzheimer’s Disease Data Initiative (AD Data Initiative, <https://www.alzheimersdata.org/>) given that the AD Workbench serves as a product that supports the EPND technical hub.

Figure 2. EPND’s value proposition

2. DATA SUMMARY

Purpose and relation to the project

Both the generation and the re-use of the data are directly related to the main objective of the project, which is to develop a screening toolbox platform for early accurate diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease, and AD dementia preventive therapies. To this end, pre-existing data from multiple partner sources (e.g., imaging investigations, fluid biomarkers, genetics, clinical history, and results from several cognitive, behavioural, and functional tests) will be used. In addition, data will be generated in the context of the tasks from WP1, WP2, and WP3. Figure 3 depicts the expected tasks related to data management, and their connections, in the project.

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Figure 3 Data flow overview

As a first step to mapping the data within the project, WP6 will work with partners and cohort owners to collect a standardised set of metadata, the content of which will be defined in conjunction with them. To this end, an initial list of potential metadata fields has been provided to the partners as part of a questionnaire during the kick-off meeting held in June 2024 (see Annex 1). The initial set of proposed fields was extracted from metadata attributes collected in previous projects (EJP-RD, EPND Silver Catalogue, LeMHR, DUC/CCE) that were relevant to AD-RIDDLE. The responses from the questionnaire will be used to refine the list of metadata fields, which will be reviewed with resource custodians. The metadata fields identified will be checked for compatibility with the metadata schemes deployed in the EPND hub to allow cross-compatibility and for leveraging resources from the EPND catalogue. Once defined, a repository will be set up in the project to allow the collection of the relevant metadata from the partners, conducted via a self-service web tool, completed by the relevant people on the project for their resources. Partners will be able to update their entries to reflect the changes in their resources over time. Previous tools of this type developed by partner ULEIC could import and export the metadata in the JSON format. The collected metadata will then be used to construct a data map of what data is where, which will be shared with the partners to allow them to convey what data they will require during the project. Via this process it is envisaged that the data flows within the project will be identified, which can then be facilitated by the relevant partners (WP6, WP7, and WP9). Again, the partners will be able to revise this as the project progresses to allow the data flow to represent the current needs within the project.

Types and formats of data

A clear description of the data types and formats of data that will be used during the project will be provided as the result of Task 6.1 (Creation of a project-wide Data Map) using tools like the questionnaire in Annex 1 of the present report.

Tabular data

AD-RIDDLE will collect a variety of data that will be used in the different WPs, for example in the development of the predictive algorithms and decision support toolkits.

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- The genotype of some of the patients will allow the inclusion of genetic information such as the characterization of the APOE allele and GWAS.
- Cognitive function of the participants will be evaluated with different cognitive tests that may include Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE), Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA), Clinical Dementia Rating (CDR), and Neuropsychological test batteries.
- Sociodemographic data, lifestyle variables, and the concomitant medication of the patients will be assessed via personal clinical histories.
- Fluid biomarkers will be recorded and may include A β 42, A β 40/42, p-Tau 181, p-Tau 217, p-Tau 231, NfL, GFAP (for plasma) and A β 42, T-tau and P-tau (for cerebrospinal fluid).

Re-using existing data

Data used within AD-RIDDLE will incorporate data originating from other (ongoing or finalized) studies and different established cohorts.

Origin of data

Retrospective data

The retrospective data comes mainly from the eleven cohorts from different research institutions, universities, and hospitals including: GEDOC (Region Stockholm, Sweden), Bio-FINDER (Lund, Sweden), CHARIOT Pro (London and Edinburgh, United Kingdom), Kuopio research cohort (UEF, Finland), ALFA+ and Beta-AARC (BarcelonaBeta Research Centre, Spain), GERICO (UNIPG, Italy), Amsterdam cohorts and Amsterdam Twin study (Amsterdam, Netherlands), EPND (multicenter, International), and Netherlands Consortium Dementia cohorts (multicenter, Netherlands).

Prospective data

Prospectively data will be collected in WP2 and WP3 that will be further used for developing and validating predictive algorithms for at-risk/early AD disease stages (WP4).

A 3-year real-world testing study will be conducted at 8 sites in 6 European countries (Sweden, Finland, The Netherlands, Spain, Italy, United Kingdom), and will be co-designed together with Consortium partners. Subjects will be recruited from general populations, in primary care or memory clinic settings, targeting participants across the entire continuum from brain-at-risk to preclinical and prodromal AD.

Both the availability of the type of data and the number of visits of the participants depend on the research cohort and will be assessed during the elaboration of the common data template.

The estimated number of participants in real-world testing study are:

- digital cognitive assessments: ~20,000 across all sites,
- BBMs measurements: ~3,000 with cognitive symptoms, and 10,000-12,000 general population (including preclinical AD).

Data from each sub-study (i.e., at each clinical site) will be obtained directly from the relevant digital tools (e.g. cognitive assessment tools), and also from electronic case report forms (eCRF) entered into a data capture system.

Data collection will follow a standardized data model, for which maximum alignment with existing standards will be sought. A secure federated data system is more suitable for this study than centralised data collection, i.e., facilitating harmonisation and joint analyses while allowing each sub-study/site and involved industry

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partners the appropriate level of control concerning tool- or site-specific data collection and sharing. Data analysis will be conducted on pseudonymised (personal identifiers removed and replaced by a unique code for each study participant). Data will be collected, quality checked, and managed according to a pre-specified data management plan. Planned data analyses will be described in a statistical analysis plan, and results and methods described in a clinical study report.

The implementation research part will have its own data analysis plan which will define key variables and a qualitative codebook. The analysis plan will lay out an integrated mixed methods approach using qualitative data, as well as quantitative data gathered from sites.

Data utility

Data collected and generated by AD-RIDDLE will be useful for research purposes – not only on biomarker validation, but also in terms of natural history of the disease, decision-making algorithm generation for early detection and optimised prognosis, diagnosis and treatment. Implementation work will ascertain data relevant to the challenges related to the real-life implementation of biomarker-centred pathways in clinical settings. The development of the foreseen screening toolbox platform will potentially be beneficial to several groups related to the neurodegenerative disease research and medical community:

- **Patients at risk of AD dementia** (preclinical and prodromal AD) and older adult citizens (age 60+ years) will benefit from access to timely personalized, evidence-based preventive therapies.
- **Healthcare professionals** will benefit from validated tools that will allow them to identify at-risk patients and select appropriate preventative action.
- **Researchers** will benefit from validated biomarkers to accelerate the development of precision therapies to prevent or delay AD dementia.
- **Healthcare systems** will benefit from evidence that helps to identify the right patients, at the right time, for the right interventions to improve treatment outcomes and decrease resource utilization.
- **Health technology developers** will benefit from understanding barriers to the adoptions and operationalization of validated tools to improve commercialization efforts.

The following table summarises data-related aspects in AD-RIDDLE according to the initial plans:

Type of data generated	Data to be processed in this project include: 1) data from existing observational cohorts and interventional RCTs for development of predictive algorithms for risk/disease and prevention potential, 2) data generated through real-world testing of digital cognitive assessments and blood biomarkers, 3) routine care data processed during the real-world biomarker testing study, and 4) data collected from healthcare professionals during implementation research. These include mainly longitudinal, patient-level demographic and health data (e.g., cognitive functioning, fluid and imaging biomarkers, diagnoses and medical history, lifestyle-related variables), and questionnaires and qualitative data related to patients’ and healthcare professionals’ experiences during the real-world testing study.
Access to existing data	For prediction algorithms development, data will be accessed mainly from sources directly maintained by consortium partners. Other relevant datasets may be selected as needed from the EPND catalogue and the Amyloid Biomarker Study, accessible through existing networks and collaborations.

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Findability of data	Metadata and contextual information about the project will be shared via relevant repositories in AD/dementia research, e.g., resources developed in the EPND project, the EMIF (www.emif.eu) catalogue and/or the Dementia Platform UK (DPUK, https://www.dementiasplatform.uk/). Other resources may be identified during the project since AD/dementia is an area of rapid development.
Accessibility of data	The ability to share patient-level data collected through routine care with external researchers for purposes outside this project is likely to be limited for governance and regulatory reasons. However, some of the data generated during the real-world testing study can likely be shared after pseudonymisation.
Interoperability of data	To facilitate analyses, a common data model will be developed and applied throughout the project as appropriate. This will enable easy transfer of analysis tools (statistical tools, etc.) as well as pooling of data if required for analytical purposes. The OMOP standard will be preferably used for observational data whenever possible. CDISC standards will be preferably used for interventional RCT data.
Reusability of data	The modular, toolbox platform approach will enable more flexibility regarding reuse of data imported from various sources by different applications.
Curation and storage	Data obtained for work on prediction algorithms or generated from the real-world testing study will be retained according to retention policies agreed through research ethics and data release applications, likely spanning 2-3 years after conclusion of the study. Routine care data processed during the project will be retained in accordance with local policies agreed with the data owner (local healthcare provider).

3. FAIR DATA

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data identification

The use of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) must be carefully considered, as DOIs/URIs must be generated through an authorized provider. Most providers require a basic level of metadata, which needs to be discussed with the data-generating and data-owning partners to ensure they consent to their resources having a publicly available permanent link. Additionally, as mentioned in the introduction, different providers collect varying minimal metadata. This metadata must be approved by the partners to confirm their agreement on sharing it. Therefore, a discussion with the partners will be held to decide on the most suitable permanent link provider based on these considerations.

Data format

One of the project groups currently has tools that use JSON format for all importing and exporting. However, we are open to considering other formats, time permitting, depending on the complexity of integrating these formats into the existing tools.

In terms of the retrospective datasets themselves (i.e. those already collected in previous and ongoing cohort studies), a variety of formats has been used. Harmonisation will be performed as a discrete intervention according to the project needs.

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Open science principles

Project deliverables will be shared openly where possible, with limitations based on restrictions regarding data sharing (e.g., patient confidentiality and regulatory requirements, protection of background intellectual property of consortium partners). A research version of the AD-RIDDLE toolbox platform will be made available for bona fide researchers to use for further research, development, and validation, and to support work on biomarkers for prediction and prevention of AD/dementia, allowing development of effective personalised interventions. During the project, data will be managed in line with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles (as stated below).

3.2. Making data openly accessible

Data accessibility

The accessibility of the data needs to be carefully considered and discussed among the members of the consortium. Therefore, this section will be further developed and updated in the coming period. A more concise approach will be available in D9.6 Updated Data Management Plan.

Data harmonisation and management, powered by an innovative data platform

Within this project, a great deal of data will be generated, processed, analysed, and moved around between partners and supporting infrastructures. Some data will be managed and exploited within the EPND Technical Hub, which enables secure storage, discovery, sharing, and single- or multi-team analyses, and utilises certain features and functionality of the AD Data Initiative’s AD Workbench. However, it is not practical to have all relevant data at all stages for all purposes placed in and analysed within this single ‘reservoir’ or ‘central data facility.’ Instead, much data will also or instead follow other paths between partners and sites, and the project will optimise this approach by actively tracking, recording, and ‘orchestrating’ the necessary data flows. This will extend beyond primary data to encompass metadata, results and algorithms, and deal with issues such as data formats/transformations, sharing conditions/governance, and wider collaboration/sharing with the community. As the project develops, these flows/processes will be adjusted and further optimised, via an iterative approach involving design, implementation, and feedback. The approach will also support information flows and requirements relevant to academic/research work in the project (e.g., cohort data, algorithm development, assay optimisation), as well as data interactions involving healthcare settings that are implementing the project’s diagnostics solution.

3.3. Making data interoperable

To facilitate analyses, common data models will be promoted and applied throughout the project as appropriate. This will enable easy transfer of analysis tools (statistical tools, etc.) as well as pooling of data if required for analytical purposes. This will however focus on the specific needs for the project’s purposes, and therefore will follow a ‘just in time’ approach (i.e. no widespread, universal harmonisation of all datasets is expected, as this will far exceed the scope and resourcing of AD-RIDDLE). Existing, established standards such as CDISC and OMOP will be selected as much as possible for any tasks related to data interoperability.

3.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

The data will be accessed and used in compliance with all applicable laws and regulations and pursuant to and in compliance with the terms and conditions (including the Access Rights granted) under the AD-RIDDLE Consortium Agreement.

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Specific provisions for data re-use will be further explained once the final data sharing and management approaches are decided.

4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

All data within AD-RIDDLE is intended to follow the FAIR principles, and therefore, these costs are embedded within the project budget.

The fact of working with retrospective cohorts from different entities makes it difficult to separate data collection costs from e.g., databasing or quality control. Outstanding costs related to making data findable, interoperable, and accessible by external audiences after the project end date will be factored into the sustainability plans.

5. DATA SECURITY

Both retrospective and prospective data storage will be subject to different security policies that may depend on the used platforms and/or repositories. Therefore, specific provisions for data security will be further explained once the final data sharing and management approaches are decided.

6. ETHICAL ASPECTS

The project entails the processing of the following: 1) data from existing observational cohorts and interventional clinical trials for the development of predictive algorithms for risk/disease and prevention potential, 2) data generated through real-world testing of digital cognitive assessments and blood biomarkers, 3) routine care data processed during the real-world biomarker testing study, and 4) data collected from healthcare professionals during implementation research. These include mainly longitudinal, patient-level demographic and personal health information (PHI), questionnaires and qualitative data related to patients and healthcare professionals' experiences during the real-world testing study.

Retrospective analysis of already collected health data poses little risk to patients except for potential breaches of personal integrity that could result from disclosure of PHI. This risk will be minimised by the measures described below.

The prospective study collects PHI and may impact the diagnostic process. The impact may vary between clinical sites, depending on the status of digital and/or blood biomarkers, i.e. whether they have or will receive approval for use in standard healthcare, and also on the type of clinical setting (e.g. primary versus specialised care). As a general principle, site-specific standard healthcare procedures and ethics requirements will be followed. Ethical aspects will be covered in detail in the real-world testing study protocol. The core protocol will address general aspects applicable to all clinical sites, while site-specific appendices to the core protocol will address ethical aspects at each site, considering the type of clinical setting(s), risk/disease stage of the population to be recruited, and local/national requirements. Amendments to the protocol including appendices will be made as needed if the approval status of various biomarkers for use in standard healthcare changes over time, and new disease-modifying drugs may also receive regulatory approval. The study will be conducted at each site only after the respective site has received approval from the relevant local ethics committee, including for protocol amendments where applicable. Communication of biomarker information to participants will be conducted according to site-specific standard healthcare procedures, ethics requirements (e.g. where applicable, duty of care to communicate health information with established clinical significance), and considering also existing guidelines on biomarkers disclosure (e.g., European Academy of Neurology/European Alzheimer's Disease

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Consortium position statement on diagnostic disclosure, biomarker counseling, and management of patients with mild cognitive impairment. *Eur J Neurol.* 2021;28:2147–2155. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ene.14668>).

All participants will receive standard care as per established local/national procedures.

As it will be made clear to patients that participation in the study is entirely voluntary, and they can leave the study at any time without giving a reason, we believe the additional burden on patients from the study will be limited.

In relation to the blood biomarkers assessment, collection of blood samples can cause little pain, but as a clinical routine, it is commonly accepted as a small risk for the study participants with almost no additional risks with minimal additional discomfort (e.g., transient, but unethical local bruises). For the retrospective analysis, participants provided consent for the use of the previously collected blood samples for additional research hypothesis in future studies, hence, the additional biomarkers measures do not imply any additional risk related to blood tests for the participants, as it would be the case with the newly collected samples, for which ethical approval will be sought, as well as written informed consent from the participants.

Compliance with ethical principles and relevant legislations

It is assumed that the studies that compose the observational and clinical trials cohorts contributing to the project have obtained ethical approval. Additional ethical approvals by research ethics committees in each country involved will be sought for the new studies.

Data accessible to the project team will be pseudonymised (personal identifiers replaced with a code unique to the patient) and identifiable information will have been removed so that individual patient identities cannot be determined. Results will only be disclosed at the group level so that information on individual patients cannot be discerned. For prospective studies, informed consent will be obtained from participants prior to inclusion into the studies. Measures will be taken to ensure data security and avoid disclosure of personal identifiable information in accordance with applicable regulations.

References to WP and deliverables

There is a specific task in WP7 (7.1) addressing the social and ethical implications of the project. This task will develop a scoping review and guidance and recommendations in relation to the value and acceptability of the developed tools, processes and methodologies.

Informed consent

Consortium partners have extensive experience with clinical research including research ethics procedures and requirements in the relevant countries.

Each member of the consortium will be responsible for inviting patients for participation, administering and recording informed consent and ensuring data is collected in accordance with the original study protocol. All studies (retrospective and prospective) may be submitted for review by research ethics committees in each country involved.

7. OTHER ISSUES

All the AD-RIDDLE project's centres are subject to their respective national/local norms and regulations, as well as governance/ethical approval procedures.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1

AD-RIDDLE_Data_Survey

I acknowledge AD-RIDDLE will use the personal data provided hereunder in accordance with the privacy statement: <https://ad-riddle.org/privacy>

1. Name *

2. Institution / organization *

3. Email

4. What information about the bioresources in the project would you like us to capture? The main areas we have identified thus far are below, please select all that you feel should apply:

- Study/dataset Name
- Abstract/description of study/dataset
- Type of Neurodegenerative disease (if not AD)
- Keywords
- Locations covered
- Longitudinal vs single visit - cross-sectional
- Researchers contact details
- Point of contact for study/dataset (email/URL)
- Data Controller
- Organisation
- Publications
- Use Conditions
- Funders
- Number of participants
- Available samples - e.g. CSF, Serum, Plasma, DNA, Saliva, Faeces, Urine
- Imaging scans collected - type, protocol, instrument
- Markers included in study/dataset

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Participant ethnicities included

Age range of participants

5. Optional: List other fields/information that you feel should be captured

6. What data do you already have, will be producing, or using during the project?

7. Does the method of classification of AD stage matter? (i.e. biomarker, image, or cognitive test) Please provide your thoughts on this: